

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**EVALUATION OF RISK FACTORS OF DIETARY HABITS
AND OBESITY AND THEIR IMPACTS ON BREAST CANCER**¹Dr Maryam Nisar, ²Dr Maryam Bano, ³Dr Maryam Abd u razzaq¹Allama Iqbal Medical College, Lahore²Dow University of Health Sciences – Sindh Medical College³WMO, BHU Bojhi kot, DHA Sargodha

Article Received: January 2020 Accepted: February 2020 Published: March 2020

Abstract:

Objective: The aim of this study is to assess the risk factors of dietary habits and obesity on the breast cancer in Lahore, Pakistan.

Methodology: This research work carried out on newly detected 40 patients of breast cancer Patient-Group and 40 willing healthy persons for Control-Group with no detection of cancer in them or past history of cancer in their family. The duration of this research work was from July 2019 to December 2019.

Results: Average age of menarche, age at menopause and age at first delivery were 13 ± 1.17 , 44.33 ± 2.39 and 22.6 ± 3.78 in patient group and 12.3 ± 0.95 , 46.71 ± 2.41 and 21.6 ± 2.99 years in control group correspondingly. The average values of body mass index were 28.1 ± 6.75 kg/m² in patient group and 30.1 ± 6.18 kg/m² in control group (P value > 0.05). We determined that use of fiber and Vitamin-C has the capability to reduce the risk of Breast Cancer. Smoking and eating fast are some important risk factors of breast cancer (P value < 0.05).

Conclusion: This research work showed that there are association among menarche age, age at menopause, age at time of first delivery, fast eating, habit of cigarette smoking and breast cancer. Contrariwise, there are some negative associations between breast cancer and utilization of Vitamin-C and fiber. Finding show that there is an association between breast cancer and various life style factors and decrease in risk of the development of breast cancer can be obtained through changes in dietary habits.

KEY WORDS: Breast Cancer, Menopause, Menarche, Vitamin-C, Questionnaire, Dietary Habits.

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Please cite this article in press Maryam Nisar et al., *Evaluation Of Risk Factors Of Dietary Habits And Obesity And Their Impacts On Breast Cancer*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(03).

INTRODUCTION:

Breast cancer is very frequent occurring type of cancer in the world and the occurrence of this complication is very high in our country [1]. It is also the very common cause of death induced by cancer in females [2]. The incidence rate of breast cancer is very high in the countries which are developed as compared to countries which are under development but rate of mortality is very low in developed countries [2]. Geographical differences like lifestyles and exposure to environment are the most important factors in the rate of incidences of breast cancer in different regions [3]. Dietary habits can have association with the incidence of breast cancer [4]. In accordance to WHO, obesity and fatness pose serious health issues [5]. Variety of the chronic diseases are the outcome of obesity as DM (Diabetes Mellitus) and cancer [6]. There is an association between high BMI and high values of estradiol and testosterone in post-menopausal females who are without breast cancer. Body mass index functions as a risk factor of cancer regardless of the values of estrogen, which states that the risk of breast cancer is influenced by processes far from the stimulation of estrogen of breast [7].

There is extensive investigation on the impacts of dietary habits on incidence of breast cancer but still all the findings are inconsistent as well as inconclusive [8]. Project of EPIC (European Prospective Investigation of Cancer), including about 520000 persons from ten different countries of Europe, is trying to find out the relationship between cancer and lifestyles. The main rationale of EPIC is to state the association between dietary habits and types of cancer in following years. According to EPIC's research, the risk of breast cancer among women who intake high amount of the fat is higher as compared to the females who intake lower amount of saturated fat [9].

METHODOLOGY:

This research work performed on newly detected forty patients of breast cancer having 18 years of age or above who got treatment from Oncology

Department of Jinnah Hospital, Lahore patient group 40 willing persons without cancer and past history of cancer in their family control group. The duration of this study was from July 2019 to December 2019. All the patients underwent a face to face interview to fill the questionnaire Performa. There were three types of questions in the questionnaire as characteristics of demography, dietary and general habits. All the participants who were willing to participate were only the part of this research work. We selected maximum amount of the patients that can be assessed in the permitted period of this research work. Ethical committee of the institute gave the permission to conduct this research work. We also obtained written consent from every patient.

The determination of the nutritional condition of all participants carried out by the questionnaire of the food frequency. The assessment of the nutritional values carried out with the utilization of the Nutrient Base Program [10]. The measurement of weight of body of the patients carried out with light clothes and removed shoes with the utilization of the Body Composition Analyzer UM073. We measured the BMI (Body Mass index) by standard formula [6]. Patients present with pregnancy, past history of cancer or having less than eighteen years of age were not the participants of this research work. We used SPSS V.22 for the statistical analysis of the collected information. We presented the results in averages and standard deviations as well as in frequencies. We used the Chi-square test for the comparison of the characteristics of demography of the patients. The calculations of the relative risks carried out as OR (Odds Ratio) with 95% CI (Confidence Interval). P value of less than 0.05 was significant.

RESULTS:

The characteristics of demography are present in Table-1. The average age of females in patient group and control group was 51.8 ± 12.9 and 50.9 ± 13.05 years respectively. The educational status was high among females of Patients Group as compared to the patients of control group.

Demographic characteristics		Patient Group (n:40)		Control Group (n:40)	
		n	%	n	%
Age (years)	< 29	1	2.5	1	2.5
	30 - 39	6	15	8	20
	40 - 49	10	25	9	22.5
	50 - 59	11	27.5	11	27.5
	> 60	12	30	11	27.5
	X ± SD	51.8 ± 12.9		50.9 ± 13.05	
	Min-max	23 - 83		22 - 84	
Educational Status	Primary school	14	35	21	52.5
	Secondary school	1	2.5	3	7.5
	High school	12	30	4	10
	University	13	32.5	12	30
Occupation	Unemployed	22	55	24	60
	Government official	6	15	3	7.5
	Self-employed	1	2.5	1	2.5
	Others	11	27.5	12	30
Marital Status	Married	36	90	34	85
	Single	4	10	6	15

Majority of the females in both groups were housewives. 90% females in Patient Group and 85.5% females in Control group were living their married lives. The relationship between occurrence of breast cancer and reproductive features are present in Table-2.

Reproductive Factors	Patient Group (n:40)	Control Group (n:40)	P	OR	95% CI	P
Menarche Age (years)	13.03 ± 1.17	12.35 ± 0.95	0.607	1.835	1.102 - 3.055	0.002*
Age at First Birth (years)	22.64 ± 3.78	21.63 ± 2.99	0.178	1.195	1.003 - 1.424	0.046*
Number of Children	2 (1 - 6)	2 (1 - 3)	0.911	2.488	0.886 - 6.99	0.084
Menopause Age (years)	44.33 ± 2.39	46.71 ± 2.41	0.556	1.744	1.176 - 2.585	0.006*

The age of menarche and age at first delivery were high and average age at time of menopause was low in the group of patient group than control group ($P < 0.05$). Average age of menarche was 13 ± 1.17 years in patient group and 12.30 ± 0.95 years in control group [OR: 1.835(95% CI= 1.102-3.055)].

Average age at first delivery was 22.6 ± 3.78 years in females of patient group and 21.60 ± 2.990 years in females of control group [OR: 1.195 (95% CI= 1.003-1.424)]. Median of number of children in both groups was two in both groups [OR: 2.488 (95% CI= 0.886-6.99)]. Menopausal age was 44.33 ± 2.39 years in patient group and 46.71 ± 2.41 years in females of control group [OR: 1.744 (95% CI= 1.176-2.585)]. Table-3 shows the logistic regression analyses of intakes of dietary energy, body mass index and breast cancer.

Table-III: Logistic Regression Of Dietary Energy, Nutrient Intakes, BMI And Breast Cancer

Energy and Nutrients	Patient Group (n:40)		Control Group (n:40) X ± SD		P	OR	95% CI	p
	X	± SD	X	± SD				
Energy (kcal)	1810.7	± 427.5	1800.8	± 371.36	0.001	1	0.999 - 1.001	0.911
Saturated Fatty Acid (g)	37.3	± 10.84	35.9	± 9.32	0.014	1.014	0.97 - 1.06	0.53
Vitamin A (µgRE)	1541.2	± 882.25	1516.4	± 469.3	0.001	1	0.999 - 1.001	0.874
Vitamin E (mg)	11.6	± 3.85	11.3	± 2.87	0.023	1.024	0.899 - 1.168	0.717
Vitamin C (mg)	96.5	± 36.34	150.5	± 43.77	-0.03	0.97	0.956 - 0.983	0.001*
Fiber (g)	19.4	± 5.24	27.2	± 6.86	-0.02	0.813	0.738 - 0.897	0.001*
BMI (kg/m ²)	28.1	± 6.75	30.1	± 6.18	0.541	1.719	0.400 - 7.388	0.466

Average BMI was 28.1 ± 6.75 kg/m² and 30 ± 6.18 kg/m² in patient group and control group respectively. Risk of breast cancer, general and eating habits are present in Table-4. The findings show that breast cancer risk is about 3.5 times high in females whose speed of eating is fast than the females who have low speed of eating [OR=3.562 (95% CI=1.183-10.731)]. Total 17 patients and 20 controls stated their smoking status.

Table-IV: Logistic Regression Of Eating, General Habits And Breast Cancer

Parameters		Patient Group (n:40)		Control Group (n:40)		OR	95% CI	p
		No	Percent	No	Percent			
Eating rate	Slow	8	20	18	45			
	Medium	13	32.5	10	25	2.93	0.906 - 9.442	0.073
	Fast	19	47.5	12	30	3.56	1.183 - 10.731	0.024*
Smoking status	Never Active Smoker	23	57.5	20	50			
	Ever Active Smoker	17	42.5	20	50	1.76	1.036 - 2.997	0.036*
Alcohol consumption	No	32	77.5	36	85			
	Yes	8	20	4	10	1.36	0.221 - 8.346	0.742

There are many factors responsible for breast cancer including genetic and environmental factors. Breast cancer is a serious issue of health for general

DISCUSSION:

population [11]. The risk of breast cancer has association with the different reproductive, hereditary and hormonal factors [12]. Majority of the patients of breast cancer as well as rate of mortalities because of breast cancer are present among females having greater than fifty years of age [13]. There was high occurrence of this complication among workers (45%) [14]. One other research work found that 31.80% patients of breast cancer were present in the age group of 40 to 49 years [15]. It is well acknowledged that age of menarche, age at first time of delivery and age at menopause are the important risk factors for breast cancer [16]. In a Korean research work, the average age of menarche in females suffering from breast cancer was 14.6±1.79 years and average age at first birth was 25.45±5.26 years [17]. It is observance that risk of breast cancer was higher for premenopausal females at the similar age than postmenopausal females [18].

Association between intake of fiber and breast cancer risk was under examination in many research works [19]. In one research work, 10 g/day rise in the intake of fiber was present with an association with a reduction by 7.0% in risk of breast cancer [2]. It is acknowledged fact that the intake of the fiber reduces the breast cancer risk. Vitamin also plays an important role in the decrease of the diseases in human and improves health. Vitamins also plays an important role in the prevention of cancer but there are no proper findings of this topic [11]. One research work found that folic acid, lycopene, Vitamin-C, Vitamin-E and vitamin B6 are in inverse association with the risk of breast cancer [12]. Habit of cigarette smoking also an important risk factor of carcinogenesis because of various mutagens. One research work stated that there is association between the smoking intensity and breast cancer.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of this current research work discovered that there is strong association between breast cancer and age of menarche, age at the time of first delivery, age at the time of menopause, quick eating and habit of cigarette smoking, on other hand, there was negative association between breast cancer and utilization of fiber and Vitamin-C and fiber. We can conclude that the risk of the development of the breast cancer can be decreased with the alterations in lifestyle and balanced diet. There is need of further research works to consolidate the findings of this research work.

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